

TECHNOLOGIES FOR DEVELOPMENT OF GENERAL COMPETENCES OF PRESCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. *The article examines the problems of improving the professional competences of educators, the experience of working on the formation of the professional competence of young educators through the implementation of the methodical support model is presented. The stages of formation of professional competence are disclosed.*

Keywords: *quality of education, professional qualification, preschool teacher, methodical support model, training of educators.*

Currently, in the conditions of the developing market relations, every specialist who has a strong competitive position in the labor market should have professional competence and consistently develop social competence in the process of socialization.

The educator of a preschool educational organization is one of the popular modern pedagogical professions. In the modern sense, an educator is a person who takes responsibility for the state of life and the development of another person and carries out education. An educator should have the following: benevolent, sincere, friendly, polite, have a sense of humor, be patient, build relationships with children, prevent and resolve conflicts, self- He should supplement his knowledge by educating himself, know the method of preschool

Competence is derived from the English word "competence" and means "ability". If we pay attention to the meaning of competence, it means "to be able to effectively use knowledge, high experience to demonstrate professional competence, skill and talent" in the activity. , the analysis of pedagogical processes allows to realize any development of the child from the point of view of scientific research. To do this, it is necessary to equip young people with knowledge, to restore our national values, to restore our spirituality, to introduce them to world culture, the masterpieces of our culture, and to raise them to be physically healthy and spiritually mature. For this, the ability of everyone to demand and control himself is a guarantee of the fulfillment of the requirements set by our state for pre-school education organizations. The area includes:

Maintaining and strengthening the child's health.

- Increase mental ability.
- Formation of beliefs and views that correspond to the ideological and mental principles of our national value and spirituality.
- Formation of love for motherland, social activity.

To inculcate the sense of friendship, honesty and hard work in the young generation. An educator must have a high level of pedagogical skills, such as communication skills, thoroughly master the laws of pedagogical technique, speech, face, hand, leg and body movements, mime, gesture, pantomime). An educator should be able to observe children, correctly analyze the reasons for their behavior, and use tools that influence them. In order to make the young generation aware of the necessary knowledge, skills, and abilities, the educator must have the culture of speech and be able to reflect the following features in his speech.

- Clarity of speech.

- Voluntary speech.

Purity of speech (free from its various dialect words), expression only in literary language, jargon (words specific to professionals in a certain profession or field), barbarism (addition of foreign words to the speech expressed in the language of a certain nation inappropriate use), vulgarism (words used in actions, cursing) and conciliarism (speaking in a formal speech in inappropriate situations) should be free, and the teacher's speech should be simple, should be fluent. Professional competence does not mean the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. Also, competence requires constant enrichment of professional knowledge, learning new information, understanding important social requirements, finding new information, processing it and being able to use it in one's work

Professional competence is evident in the following cases:

1. Social competence - the ability to show activity in social relations, the ability to communicate with subjects in professional activities.

2. Special competence is preparation for organizing professional-pedagogical activity, rational solution of professional-pedagogical tasks, realistic assessment of activity results, consistent development of BKM, innovative and communicative competence is noticeable on the basis of this competence. They contain the following content:

1) psychological competence - the ability to create a healthy psychological environment in the pedagogical process, to organize positive communication with students and other participants of the educational process, to be able to understand and eliminate various negative psychological conflicts in a timely manner;

2) methodical competence - the methodical rational organization of the pedagogical process, the correct determination of the forms of educational or educational activity, the ability to choose methods and tools in accordance with the purpose, the ability to effectively use methods, the successful use of tools;

3) information competence - searching for, collecting, sorting, processing necessary, important, necessary, useful information in the information environment and using it purposefully, appropriately, and effectively;

4) creative competence - a critical and creative approach to pedagogical activities, the ability to demonstrate one's own creative skills;

5) innovative competence - putting forward new ideas on improving the pedagogical process, improving the quality of education, increasing the effectiveness of the educational process, and successfully implementing them into practice;

6) communicative competence - the ability to communicate sincerely with all participants of the educational process, including students, to be able to listen to them, to have a positive influence on them.

3. Personal competence - to consistently achieve professional growth, to increase the level of competence, to demonstrate one's internal capabilities in professional activity. 4. Technological competence - mastering advanced technologies that enrich professional and pedagogical BKM, being able to use modern tools, techniques and technologies.

5. Extreme competence - the ability to make rational decisions and act correctly in emergency situations (natural disasters, technological process failure), when pedagogical conflicts arise.

Therefore, in order to prepare preschool children for full-fledged school education, the educator of the preschool organization must first of all learn about all the above-mentioned qualities, abilities, pedagogical-psychological skills, and the conditions for organizing classes. , should have the skills to conduct correctly, to use technologies correctly.

In the modern conditions of the reform of the preschool education system, the status of the educator is changing radically, his educational functions, accordingly, his professional and pedagogical competence, and the requirements of his professional skill level are changing. Today, in the modern system of upbringing and development of a preschool child, a creative and skilled teacher is required, who is able to develop the skills of mobilizing his personal potential.

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